

Surveillance of Rice Yellow Mottle Virus (RYMV) Infecting Rice farms in Kebbi State, Northwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

The world population is expanding substantially, necessitating increasing food production, among which is rice. However, rice production in Nigeria is being endangered by infections from numerous pathogens such as Rice yellow mottle virus. This study aims to detect rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) using PCR based method in various rice farms of the Kebbi North senatorial district. Symptoms severity scores ranged from 2.5 ± 1.3 to 1.5 ± 0.5 as observed in the field. Standard downstream molecular procedures were applied from total nucleic acids extraction to electrophoresis for final bands of rice yellow mottle virus detection. The PCR detection of rice yellow mottle virus in question was not detected in all samples even a single band apart of the ladder despite investing in upstream approaches. This might be as a result of several factors and thus, there is need to further determine what led to the negatives in all the PCR samples.

Keywords: Gel electrophoresis, Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV), Polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

1.0 Introduction

The world population is increasing significantly, necessitating the need for increasing the level of food production, among which is rice [1]. Rice (*Oryza* spp.) is grown widely in many parts of the world and is one of the major food sources for about 60% of the world's human population [2,3]. Nigeria's rice production grew from 5.7 million metric tones in 2019 to 9.0 million metric tones in 2023[3]. For the records, the major rice-producing states in Northern Nigeria are Kebbi, Borno, Kano, and Kaduna [4]. In Nigeria, Kebbi State has been recognized as one of the major rice-producing States.

Rice production is affected by several diseases. To date, 17 rice virus diseases have been reported in different parts of the world [5,6,7]. These viruses are transmitted by insect vectors (eg *Coleopterans* transmit RYMV) in persistent or

non-persistent manner and cause some common disease symptoms [1]. In Nigeria, rice production is being threatened by infections from various pathogens especially Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) which belongs to the group as the major virus infecting rice in African continent [8]. RYMV of the genus *Sobemo virus* was first reported in Nigeria in 1976 [9,10]. RYMV has restricted experimental host ranges encompassing *Oryza sativa*, and *O. barthii* showing various symptoms, such as mosaic damage, yellowing, chlorosis, stunting, necrosis parallel to veins to produce mottling and stunting are reported in infected plants, leading to loss of proper growth and reproductive functions of the plants [11,12].

Kebbi State has a very big potential in terms of rice production [13]. However, this potential is being threatened by the menace of Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV). Rice Yellow Mottle Virus disease was reported in some major rice

producing area of Kebbi state, which is contributing to low yields of rice in the State [13, 14]. Rogueing remains the major available management method for curing plant viral infectious illnesses under field circumstances. Therefore, early detection of the relevant causative agents represents the most crucial step to prevent the possible spread of the infectious disease [15]. This study seeks to use PCR based detection method to detect the prevalence of rice yellow mottle virus sequences on the rice leaf samples from the Kebbi North senatorial district being one of the rice most producing area within the state in Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample collection

Leaf samples were collected from 5 local governments in the State, Argungu, Birnin Kebbi, Bagudo, Bunza and Suru. The selection of local governments has been done on the basis of the major rice producing local governments in the State. Two Fadama areas were selected from each local government. The Fadama areas are Matanfada and Gadaga (Zaurenbaya) in Argungu, Gyale and Mashayanika in Birnin Kebbi, Zadi and Dogonruwa in Bagudo, Ketarengada and Gulba in Bunza, and Bango and Kunga in Suru. Thus, 6 samples were collected from each Fadama, making 12 samples from each local government, and a total of 60 samples in all using polythene bags and stored in a refrigerator till use.

2.2 DNA extraction

Total DNAs were isolated from rice leaf tissues using a modified Lodhi et al.[16] CTAB technique [17]. The rice leaf tissues (~ 100 mg each sample) were placed in mortar, followed by addition of 1 ml extraction buffer (2% (w/v) CTAB, 100 mM Tris-HCL (pH 8.0), 20 mM EDTA, 1.4 M NaCl) containing freshly added 2%

(w/v) polyvinylpyrrolidone-40 (PVP-40), and 1% (w/v) sodium sulfite (Na_2SO_3). The leaf materials were pulverized using a pestle. For each sample, crude extract (700 ml) was placed into 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes, vortexed, and incubated in a water bath (60°C, 30 minutes) for cell lysis. 700 mL phenol, chloroform, and isoamyl alcohol in a ratio 25:24:1 (v/v/v) were poured into the extract, vortexed, and centrifuged (13000 g, 10 min) in a microcentrifuge tube for the first clarification. About 700 mL of the aqueous layer was collected and put carefully into a fresh microcentrifuge, after which chloroform, isoamyl alcohol in ratio 24:1 (v/v) were added and centrifuged (13000 g 10 min) for second clarity. About 700 ml of the aqueous layer was carefully transferred into a fresh microcentrifuge tube and then mixed thoroughly with 75 ml of 5M NaCl and 450 ml of cold isopropanol. After incubating (-20 °C 1 h), the mixture was centrifuged (4 °C, 13000 g, 10 min) to pellet the nucleic acids. The supernatant was decanted off, and the pellet washed twice by adding 500 ml of 70% (v/v) ethanol, and then centrifuged (13000 g 10 min). The ethanol was carefully decanted and nucleic acid pellets were then dried using a DNA vacuum drier (Eppendorf centrifuge concentrator plus). The dried pellets were then reconstituted in 100 ml 1x TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 0.1 mM EDTA) and kept at -20 °C until use. The isolated DNA samples were diluted in 1:10 (v/v) in nuclease-free sterile distilled deionized water (SDW, Thermo Scientific, UK) before PCR.

2.3 Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

2.3.1 Primers

Total extracted DNAs were screened for the presence of sequences typical of the genus *Sobemovirus* by PCR. The degenerate primers set RYMVF and RYMVR (forward and reverse) were used which has been designed using primer3 software (<http://bioinfo.ut.ee/primer3/>).

Table 1 Properties of primers used for DNA extraction

Name	Sequence (5'-3')	Annealing Temp.(Tm)	MW
<i>RYMVF</i> 13	ATGGCCAGGAAGGGCAAG	67.5	5623
<i>RYMVR</i> 52	CTCCCCACCCATCCCGAGAATT	75.2	6849
<i>TRYMVR</i>	GGGCTTCGTCACCTCYAGC	64.2	5748
<i>TRYMVF</i>	CCCGCAGGACCATACTACGA	62.5	6377

However, primers for plant actin gene were also used as an internal control.

2.3.2 PCR reaction

The PCR procedure was adapted from [18]. 20 μ l of PCR master mix were set up containing 2.0 μ l PCR buffer (75 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.8, 20 mM $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4$, 0.01% (v/v) Tween 20) (Thermo Scientific, UK), 0.5 μ l dNTPs (Promega, UK), 1 μ l of each primer, 0.2 μ l Taq polymerase (Thermo Scientific, UK), 13.3 μ l molecular grade water and 2 μ l infected rice leaf DNA template. The PCR cycling was performed in a Maxygene II Thermo 1001 (California, USA). Thermo cycling conditions were designed as follows: initial denaturation at 94 °C for 5 min, followed by 30 cycles of 94 °C for 30 s, 55 °C for 30 s, and 72 °C for 1 min, followed by final extension step at 72 °C for 2 min.

2.3.3 Agarose Gel electrophoresis

Agarose gel was made using a w/v % solution. About 5g agarose powder was weighed out into a conical flask. 0.5x TBE buffer (40 mM Tris-acetate, 1 mM EDTA) was used to produce a solution. The concentration of agarose in a gel depends on the sizes of the DNA fragments to be separated. The solution was heated in a microwave to melt until transparent solution is created. 0.5 μ l SYBR safe DNA gel stain was added. The agarose solution was allowed to cool on the bench top. The comb was placed within the

gel tray, and molten agarose was poured into the tray and allowed to solidify at room temperature. The comb was removed gently and placed the gel inside the gel box.

A flowing buffer was used to cover the gel. A loading dye was added to the extracted DNA samples for separation. DNA samples were put slowly and carefully onto the gel. A 100 kb DNA marker is included with the samples. The gel was withdrawn from the gel tray and subjected to ultraviolet light. DNA bands appeared as orange luminous bands.

3.0 Results

3.1 Field assessment of RYMV symptoms in rice farms

Various phenotypic symptoms of mosaic damage, yellowing, chlorosis, stunting, necrosis, veins banding, mottling and stunting of rice were observed. However, some symptoms might not be observed phenotypically. A scoring scale 1 to 5 was used to indicate the severity of the symptoms in the field as shown in table 2 below. The most common symptoms observed in field were necrosis, mottle/yellowing and sterility of flowers, Leaf deforming, chlorosis and mottle yellowing as shown in the figure 1 below.

Fig. 1: Rice farm field showing yellowish symptoms

Table 2 Assessment of symptom severity of rice plants samples in the farmers fields.

Samples field	Types and ranges of symptoms severity			
	Mottle/yellowing	Leaf curling	Leaf necrosis	Leaf deformation
Field 1	4	2	1	1
Field 2	3	3	2	2
Field 3	5	2	2	1
Field 4	3	1	1	1
Field 5	2	4	1	1
Field 6	1	1	3	2
Field 7	2	2	1	1
Field 8	1	1	2	2
Field 9	1	2	1	1
Field 10	3	2	1	2
Mean	2.5	2	1.5	1.4
SD	1.4	0.9	0.7	0.5

3.2 Spectrophotometric quantification of the extract total Nucleic acid

The Biodrop absorbance A260/A280 ratio of extracted crude total nucleic acids (DNA/RNA) in samples were found between the range of 0.8 – 2.00 which was within the normal range making the samples to be considered pure for nucleic acids. Pure RNA has an A260/A280 ratio of ≤ 2.0 , while DNA has A260/A280 ratio of ≤ 1.8 [19]. The result of total nucleic acid in all samples shows an appreciable concentration for the analysis.

3.3 Agarose gel electrophoresis under UV light

The PCR products amplified using RTBV and RTSV (forward and reverse primer) together with plant actin gene were generated. The generated PCR products were run in 1.2% agarose gel electrophoresis using red safe as the dye and the result under UV light was obtained (Figure 2 A and B).

Figure 2A: Detection of RYMV sequence in total nucleic acid obtained from rice leaf samples collected from rice fields.

Figure 2B: Detection of actin gene in total nucleic acid obtained from rice leaf samples.

4.0 Discussion

Surveyed rice farm of the study area displayed several type symptoms ranging from yellowing to leaf deformation. The mean \pm SD symptoms severity scores ranged from 2.5 ± 1.3 to 1.5 ± 0.5 indicating moderate infection in all the farmers visited during sample collections. These symptoms were observed before the collection of some rice leaf samples on the fields surveyed. Odedara et al. [11], reported mottling and yellowing as the RYMV symptoms observed in his studied samples from Nigeria.

Total nucleic acids extraction from plant leaves are usually complicated especially due to high concentrations of polyphenols, polysaccharides, and even unknown impurities that interfere with down stream application of the total nucleic. The method used for the DNA extraction was found to yield DNA of reasonably good quality and quantity. All the DNAs obtained has their A260/A280 ratio of ≤ 1.8 . This success of getting this good quality DNAs could be attributed to the modification of the Lodhi et al. [16] subjected by Turaki et al. [17]. DNA quantification and purity check is a starting point for all DNA analysis before any further analysis is performed in a molecular biology laboratory [20]. One of the most commonly used methods to estimate nucleic acid concentration is the measurement of sample absorbance at 260nm against 280nm. The accepted range for pure DNA is ≤ 1.8

Four steps of the Lodhi et al. [16] method were modified to be user-friendly in fewer resource

laboratories of developing countries. β -mercaptoethanol (0.2%) was replaced with 1% sodium sulphite (Na_2SO_3) and the PVP-40 concentration was increased to 2%. This substitution occurred due of the toxicity and difficulties connected with disposing of β -mercaptoethanol waste in poor nations compared to sodium sulphite and PVP-40 trash. Furthermore, the usage of sodium sulphite and PVP-40 is more inexpensive compared to the use of β -mercaptoethanol.

The Lodhi et al. [16] approach employs a chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (CAA 24:1,v/v) extraction phase for removal of proteins. A modification phase was investigated by substituting CAA with phenol:chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (PCAA, 25:24:1, v/v/v) extraction. The combination of PCAA dissolves more organic compounds from the mixture compared to CAA.

The Lodhi et al. [16] approach employed ethanol with 5 M NaCl to preferentially precipitate the DNA away from the polysaccharides. A variation was produced in which ethanol was substituted with isopropanol. This occurred because DNA is less soluble in isopropanol and at low concentrations of isopropanol DNA falls out of the solution faster compared to ethanol. The precipitation was done at -20°C with varied incubation period time intervals (20 to 90 min) to choose the best incubation duration in terms of amount and purity.

PCR is typically considered the most essential and accurate tool for the diagnosis of plant viruses

[21]. However, due to the challenges associated with optimizing conditions, cost and the time needed for detection, these techniques remain less popular in plant viral diagnosis in low-income laboratories [22]. Reverse transcriptase PCR (RT-PCR), which works on the principle of cDNA synthesis from RNA-based plant viruses genome is one of the most promising approaches in plant viral diagnosis [21, 23].

RT-PCR screening for all RYMV samples were negative (Figure 2A) in the nucleic acids extract of rice leaf samples from ten (10) various locations within the Kebbi North senatorial district. This indicates that RTD is not present in the surveyed local government area. Notwithstanding, the actin gene used as an internal control shows visible fluorescent bands (Figure 2 B). This proves that DNA extraction was good and the PCR machine worked fine.

5.0 Conclusion

Rice yellow mottle virus sequence was not detected using PCR in all sample with even a single band apart from the ladder despite the use of upstream techniques. This can result from different factors, either there was no *rice yellow mottle virus* in the respective samples. With these reasons absent of *rice yellow mottle virus* can come from any of the reason mentioned.

6.0 Recommendation

It will be imperative to use a known positive control for *rice yellow mottle virus* surveillance if (RT-PCR) will be used to amplify the RYMV sequences; this is because positive control give vital information with respect to the outcome of the result. Moreso, it gives information about the quality and activities of the primer and the present or absent of the rice yellow mottle virus in the crude sample.

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8.0 References

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